

Abstract: From Inbox to Archive: Architecture for Sensitive Omics Data Submission in GHGA

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ABSTRACT

The mission of the German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA) [1,2] is to securely make highly sensitive human omics data available for research. Data and metadata submissions are one of the most important functions present as part of the GHGA science gateway. For this reason, we present here a brief overview of the architecture implemented to support the data submission process. The system leverages multiple S3 storage buckets, each designed for a specific role within the data submission pipeline.

Initially, the data is uploaded to an *Inbox* bucket using temporary client-specific credentials. Once the data is received, it is accessed from a secure data-steward virtual machine. In the VM, the data undergoes decryption and checksum validation to ensure integrity. The data is then re-encrypted using the GHGA Data Steward Kit (DSKit) and is then transferred to an *Interrogation* bucket, in which GHGA Central would have to check the submission. Finally, the data is moved to a *Permanent* bucket, where it is securely stored for long-term access and retrieval.

Before this workflow can be operational, several architectural and security requirements must be satisfied. Among them is the selection of a storage solution that ensures high availability, redundancy and data security—especially the challenges that arise when dealing with private and sensitive omics [4]. In this context, Ceph emerges as a suitable backend storage solution. Ceph's built-in support for triple data replication significantly reduces the risk of data loss, enhancing reliability. Ceph also integrates with the OpenStack S3 service, providing encryption at rest. The data is even further encrypted with the use of Crypt4GH [6], adding another layer of security. The redundancy, encryption, and access controls required for sensitive data introduce performance overhead. Ceph's high performance enables these features to run efficiently, making it well-suited for large omics datasets [3].

Despite the inherent security features provided by Ceph, potential threats from user actions, such as unauthorized deletion or modification of data, remain a major concern. This threat compromises two foundational principles of security: availability and integrity. To address these risks, fine-grained access control is implemented via access control list policies,

defining fine grained permissions on a per-bucket basis, which enforces confidentiality by ensuring only authorized users can execute specific operations. In addition, comprehensive logging mechanisms are in place. These logs capture timestamps and the user operations, fulfilling the non-repudiation requirements.

A critical component of the system's security framework is the secure distribution of credentials. A multi-step verification workflow is employed to ensure the safe access of credentials. One-time token is sent via a TOTP (Temporary One-Time Password) service, and the client is required to return this token for verification. Once verified, credentials are transmitted sequentially through the secure TOTP channel. To further enhance security, all user credentials are configured to be temporary, with a predefined time-to-live (TTL). Once expired, these credentials become invalid and are then permanently deleted, minimizing the window of potential misuse [5].

The submission is performed through the CLI. We plan on providing submission functionality through the data portal webpage, which would allow for better user experience.

Keywords—Ceph, Archive, S3, Omics data, Secure storage, Encryption, Research data management, Science gateway, Human Genome Data, NFDI, GHGA

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Krüger *et al.*, 'The GHGA Archive: Selected Updates', 2024.
- [2] J. D. O. Figueroa *et al.*, 'Developing the German Human Genome-Phenome Archive', 2022.
- [3] M. R. Effendi, N. A. Faruqi, and N. Ismail, 'Performance Analysis of Storage Media Cluster Using Ceph Platform', in *2021 8th International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Computer Science and Informatics (EECSI)*, 2021, pp. 387–390.
- [4] S. Arshad, J. Arshad, M. M. Khan, and S. Parkinson, 'Analysis of security and privacy challenges for DNA-genomics applications and databases', *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, vol. 119, p. 103815, 2021.
- [5] E. Erdem and M. T. Sandikkaya, 'OTPaaS—One Time Password as a Service', *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 743–756, 2019.
- [6] M. Young, *The Technical Writer's Handbook*. Mill Valley, CA: University Science, 1989.
- [6] A. Senf, R. Davies, F. Haziza, J. Marshall, J. Troncoso-Pastoriza, O. Hofmann, T.M. Keane, T. M. "Crypt4GH: A file format standard enabling native access to encrypted data", *Bioinformatics*, 37(17), 2753–2754, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab087>.